

THE ROLE OF THE SOUND DIRECTOR IN THE CINEMATOGRAPHY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Аннотация: В этой статье речь идет о целях и задачах роли звукорежиссера в области темпа. В кинематографе звукорежиссер является членом команды темпа, который руководит звуковым отделом. Занимается звукозаписью, работает напрямую с композитором. Задача звукорежиссера – создать звуковое сопровождение и фонограмму (фонограмму) фильма в соответствии с идейно-художественной концепцией сценариста и режиссера.

Ключевые слова: кинематография, компонентная, телевизионная, синхронная, радио, кино, видео, монтаж, дубляж, динамика, коррекция, аудиовизуальное.

Abstract: This article is about the goals and objectives of the role of the sound director in the field of pacing. In cinematography, the sound director is a member of the pacing team who manages the sound department. He is engaged in sound recording, works directly with the composer. The task of the sound director is to create the sound and soundtrack (phonogram) of the film in accordance with the ideological and artistic concept of the screenwriter and director.

Keywords: cinematography, component, television, synchronized, radio, film, video, editing, dubbing, dynamics, correction, audiovisual.

Voice is an important component of telecommunication, films, and theater performances, while it is considered essential for radio, music compositions, and concerts. During live performances by musicians, it is captivating and intriguing when there are no voice directors who can enhance the voice in a beautiful and impactful way.

Voice directing, editing, rehearsing, and strengthening require a voice director. He is responsible for making a specific impression on the listener: he

creates vocal images and sound dramaturgy, develops ideas based on vocal perception. The voice director identifies what needs to be heard and determines the technical tools to achieve it. The technical component in this profession is very important because the voice director has many possibilities in terms of equipment and its management that can implement his artistic ideas.

During the film production process, the voice director goes through all stages together with the director and the creative team. The first stage is preparation. The work begins with obtaining the film script. If the voice director is interested in the script and approves it, the next step is for the director to obtain the script. Then, the director describes in detail what and how the voice director should do, where to move, where to be, what size and how fast to be taken, and what appearance to have. Based on the director's script, the voice director creates the correct solution. The initial version is discussed with the director and the rest of the creative team.

It is possible that there may be something that the director does not like, and he may ask for another solution, and the voice director can also suggest something. After the contract is drawn up, the voice director writes a vocal description. This is a correct solution described in detail on paper, a working plan for the film. The description provides a detailed description of each frame that will occur on the screen, its size, information related to it, and instructions given based on this agreement. The voice director describes how the speech, music, and mood should be in this scene, what is possible for them to be. It provides a detailed list of all the equipment needed to be used for shooting, whether it is written on the website or obtained from the sound library, how many microphones are needed for the actors, which ones, and others. In addition, during the preparation period, the voice director compiles a detailed list of all the equipment that will be needed to be taken for shooting.

If there needs to be a singer in the film, the voice director agrees with him during the preparation period because the singer's detailed instructions on how to write music are as fast as possible, and it is possible to have it on time. Asking for

rewriting several times is not a requirement. In addition, the voice director needs to check and gain confidence in the suitability of the costumes installed in the pavilion (if available) before shooting and that they are not noisy and it is possible to write voice in these costumes. In addition, the voice director needs to ensure that actors do not wear synthetic or other "noisy" clothing when microphones are attached to them. It is reasonable to contact the costume designer for this question. The collaboration between the image director and the voice director determines how cameras and lighting devices will work without any noise. If it is planned to be synchronized with a phonogram, the voice director also prepares it during the preparation period. During the preparation period, the voice director can choose sounds from libraries, that is, from his own phonoteka. If it is arranged, it is recommended to visit objects that will be filmed before shooting, even before shooting begins, there is a lot of work for the voice director. You need to think about everything and communicate with everyone.

Transition to the next period. The main task of the sound director during the filming is to record everything necessary in high quality, and the equipment needed for the image should be fully functional. Spare cables, batteries, electronic storage devices and other small items should be sufficient and monitored. In each new location, the sound director should record all the noises that are unique and necessary to the location, as these recorded inter noises can help. In addition, in each place you need to register a microphone pause - the background noise of a certain place. It is recommended to pause every day, because the background may change the next day. If you need to hear part of the speech again, the microphone needs to be paused. So that the replayed fragment is not separated from the clean speech later. In particular, it is necessary to be careful to record all this on the site, because it is often impossible to return to the site and finish writing something. And, of course, the sound director on the set must carefully monitor the quality of the recorded material. The site should be quiet, especially mobile phones should be turned off for clear sound. It is very desirable to conduct training with sound, in which all unnecessary noise is turned

on. During the break, the sound engineer should only listen to a part of the recorded material to ensure its quality.

The next stage is post-production, which is also called editing and coloring, and it takes place in the studio. Voice dubbing is carried out. Even if clean voice has been recorded, according to the rules, you still need to re-record some materials. Here, the voice director works closely with the actor, which is not easy. In addition to monitoring the quality of the recorded material, the voice director must ensure that the actor enters his own image on the screen in a synchronized manner, as well as perform the same gestures and emotions to the same extent. The actor himself must feel, it in order to achieve the desired result. In addition, during voice dubbing, a number of technical issues need to be resolved.

The group of voice directors installs microphones, carries out soundproofing, that is, "rough" writing, based on which voice dubbing will be carried out later in the film. The beginning of the image is one of the most important tasks. The sequence of director's commands has already been established in a certain order, each of which has its own content. "Action! Get ready! Motor! Camera! Let's start!" The director's assistant starts recording the image with a clapperboard that indicates the name of the film production company (film studio), the name of the director and operator, the type of image (synchronous or silent), and the frame and dubbing number. Then, during the editing of the image and before the start of the frame, it connects the starting point of the image. It provides automatic synchronization of image and voice. Sometimes, a clapperboard placed on top of the movie camera is used.

The main task of the sound director is to record clean sound. If you cannot record a "clean" voice, then you need to provide a clear record (recording) of a rough voice that allows you to understand the replicas to put a phonogram called "lips lips". When the sound director produces a black phonogram, it is desirable to separately and completely record the atmosphere and background involved in the scene. Another important point (task): it is necessary to clearly show what equipment

colleagues are working with in the field. Let's say the film is shot in nature. The diesel generator is running, powering the lighting fixtures, the camera making noise. In this case, the final sound cannot be recorded. it is necessary to be able to see such problems in time and make changes to the recording process.

Summary

The duties of a sound director in cinematography are complex and require a strong will. Because sound is an important part of the film. After watching the movie, the audience either believes it or doesn't believe it and quickly gets bored of it. This indicates that the sound director did not work properly.

It would not be wrong to say that today, in the era of the development of modern technologies, there is a wide opportunity for sound directors. The emergence of various new technologies has become a great opportunity for sound directors to work more on themselves. For this, sound directors must have knowledge of modern technologies.

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